

Research

Study of Humanistic Education: A solution to Language Teaching in Bangladesh

Ferdousi Akter^{1}, Md. Al Mamun²*

¹Assistant Professor, Islamic University, Kushtia Bangladesh

²Assistant Prof at Jagannath University, Dhaka Bangladesh

**Corresponding author*

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Abstract: *In an antediluvian pedagogic system of language teaching, the teacher is seen to play a dominating role in the classroom instructions. But it can be argued and asserted that students can learn a second or foreign language rapidly and effectively if they are provided with an approach in ELT is such an attempt that puts its main focus on the student's inner world and places the learner's thoughts, emotions and feelings at the forefront of all linguistic development. It reduces the anxiety and offers a teaching and learning platform that not only constructs learner's knowledge but also provides them a self-realization of their own potentiality. However, this paper first presents an overview of humanistic approaches and then discusses the impacts off the humanistic approach on language teaching in general and English language teaching in particular. It also advocates for the potential applications of the humanistic approach in the language teaching context in Bangladesh.*

Keywords: *Bangladesh, language teaching.*

Introduction:

In the realm of language teaching and learning, the humanistic approach is one of the most remarkable movements. It is such an approach where the learner is seen as a whole person with physical, emotional and social features as well as cognitive characteristics. It is pertinent to educate the whole person i.e. the intellectual and the emotional dimensions” (Moskowitz,1978). It emphasizes the importance of the inner 1970, the behaviouristic and the mentalistic approaches dominated the second and some fresh suggestions came forward towards the end of the 1970s. At this juncture, the traditional roles of teaches and learners were redefined. That is to say, learners

centered classrooms replaced the previously authoritarian teaching practices. It was the work of Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow that accelerated the development of humanistic psychology in the early seventies which was called counseling learning. According to Rogers, the learners are not to be considered as a class but as a group. Curran(1972) suggests that the learners ought to be considered as clients and the teachers as 'counselors' who address the needs of the learners. He also believed that by this method, the anxiety or the fear of making a 'fool' of oneself will be lowered. Another goal of this kind of approach is to state concisely, learning out of interest and not out of compulsion. In this approach, It is also believed that students are able to self-evaluate themselves and realize their self-worth and responsibilities in the learning process that help them learn out of interest and not out of compulsion. In this approach, to state concisely, learning process becomes interesting to the students, teaching becomes plausible to the administrators.

Literature Review:

Widely discussed in the 1970s, humanistic way of language teaching integrates chiefly four methods. They are humanistic in the sense that humanistic attitude, more or less, lies in them and they spring from almost the similar psychological and philosophical concern. Now, a critical look has been given at them one by one.

- The Total Physical Response (TRP)
- Suggestopedia
- The Natural Approach
- Communicative Language Teaching(CLT)

The Total Physical Response:

Development by James Asher in 1970, the total physical response is based on the premise that just as an infant who acquires the first language by physically responding to its parents speeches one can acquire a second or foreign language too following the same approach. The teacher takes the role of the parent and helps the learners to get motivated and their self-confidence is boosted. However, the inherent weakness of this method is that it heavily relies on imperatives and is effective with only basic level learners, not with the advanced ones. This method is humanistic in the sense that it chiefly focuses on the idea that learning should be as fun and stress free as possible.

Suggestopedia:

Often considered to be the strangest of the so-called humanistic approaches suggestopedia was originally developed in the 1970s by the Bulgarian educator anxiety, increasing motivation, fostering the development of positive attitude towards language learning, promoting self-esteem as well as different learning styles” (Arnold,1999).

So, it is clear that the humanistic approach takes into account affective as well as cognitive aspects of learning when as EFL/ESL teacher attempts to extend the learner’s language competence.

Origin and Background of Humanistic Movement in Education: It was the work of Carl Rogers and Abraham Maslow that accelerated the development of humanistic psychology in the early seventies century. Which was called counseling learning? The learners are considered as a group not as a class. Curran (1972) suggests that fact, Humanistic Education evolved from and derived its basic principles from Humanistic psychology- which originated in the meddle Ages when the philosophy of humanism was born. He also believed that by this method the anxiety or the fear of making a fool of oneself will be lowered. Another goal of this kind of approach is to perceive a teacher as an empathetic helping agent in the learning process and not as a threat. In this approach humanistic approach will be described. Second, the impact of humanistic approach on language teaching will be presented Finally, Bangladeshi context will be discussed.

Relation between Humanistic psychology and Education: Though Carl Rogers applied Humanistic psychology to education Humanistic education evolved from and derived its basic principles from Humanistic psychology which originated in the Middle Ages whole the philosophy of humanism was born.

Humanistic Education and CLT:

Now a days the influence of humanistic approach strongly evident in CLT method. Gap Our updated curriculum tries to enhance the social emotional development of students over emphasis on subject matter in the classroom makes learning mechanical and ultimately this harms the balanced growth of students personality. We really need to be turning our students into individuals who believe in, respect and understand themselves respect and others who are responsible citizens and who can cope with their lives But Innovative methods such as Inter active and communicative Language Teaching. That work miracles in the west really do not

socially and culturally suit, agree or work with most Asian and south East Asian foreign Language Learners (Mahboob and Selim, 2000) because it emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language.

Nunans (1991) five features of CLT include;

1. An emphases on learners to communicate through interaction in the target language.
2. The introduction of authentic texts into the learner situation.
3. The provision of opportunities learners to focus not only on language but also on the learning process itself.
4. An enhancement of the learners own personal experiences as important contributing elements to classroom learning.
5. An attempt to link classroom language learning with language activities outside the classroom.

CLT basically focuses on improving learner's communicative competence Canale and Swain (1980, p.4) defined communicative competence in terms of four components:

- I. Grammatical competence words and rule.
- II. Socio. Appropriate
- III. Discourse competence: Cohesion and Cober
- IV. Strategic competence appropriate use of communicating strategic.

Any teaching practice that helps students develop their communicative competence in an authentic context is deemed an acceptable and beneficial from of instruction. In the classroom CLT often takes the form of learning and group work requiring negotiation and co-operation be taken into consideration. Fluency based an activity that encores learners to develop their confidence role plays in which students practice and develop language functions, as well as judicious use of grammar and pronounce tic on focused activities.

Merits of CLT:

CLT is a holistic approach: It does not focus only on the traditional structural Syllabus. It takes into consideration the communicative dimension of language. CLT provides vitality and motivation within the classroom CLT is a learner contested approach, It capilizes on the interests and needs of the learners. Students still perceive their teachers in the traditional superior role and hence they cannot take on the Joint responsibility in their own learning process. This is where the function of humanistic educationist important as it is perhaps one of the few means by which

learners can be somewhat equipped, male ready or prepared for such student method, According to Huitt's (1995) systems model of human behavior the primary emphasis of humanistic education is on the regulatory system and the effective emotional system. The development of these systems is often overlooked in our present education system.

Basic principles of Humanistic Education:

According to Gage and Berliner (1991), some key underlying principles of humanistic education are

1. Give freedom to choose:

Students will learn more easily and quickly if it is something they need and want to learn, so, they should be allowed to choose what they want to learn.

2. Importance of knowing how to learn:

Students should be inspired to be self-motivated and take the responsibility to their own learning.

3. Self-evaluation is the first priority: The emphasis here is on internal development and self-persuasion.

4. Humanistic education focuses on the whole person: here feelings are as important as facts:

5. Students learn best in a non-threatening environment.

The environment should be psychologically and emotionally as well as physically non-threatening.

Language teaching and humanistic Approach:

Gertrude Moskowitz (1978) gives specific strategies of foreign language teaching which can help a teacher in integrating humanistic concepts into the existing curriculum. Below are the fundamental tenets of humanistic education:

1. Personal growth, including realizing one's full potential, one of the primary goals of education.
2. The development of human values should be ensured.
3. The learners should be engaged emotionally as well as intellectually.
4. Behaviors that cause anxiety and stress should be avoided.
5. Learners should be actively involved in the learners' process.

6. Learners can and should take responsibilities for their own learning. Learners can and should take responsibilities for their own learning. Stevick,(1990) mentions five emphases of humanism which serve as a guideline to the humanist teachers .

- a. Feeling: Personal emotions and aesthetic appreciations should be encouraged. Learners feelings are respected in a humanistic class room.
- b. Social relation: This encourages friendship and co- operation. The learner develops interpersonal skills that accelerate language learning.
- c. Responsibility: This aspect accepts the need for public scrutiny, criticism, and correction and disapproves of whomever or what ever denies their importance.
- d. Intellect: It includes knowledge, reason and understanding. This fought against whichever interferes with the free exercise of the mind.
- e. Self actualization: It is concerned with the quest for full realization of one's own deepest true qualities. This aspect believes that the pursuit of uniqueness brings about liberation since conformity leads to enslavement.

Implications of Humanistic Approach on Education:

Affective education recognizes that any one who is teaching is dealing with students and their feelings. Humanistic education aims at self actualization and it considers the fact that learning is affected by what students feel about themselves, and when they feel about themselves they are to be high achievers. Arthur Combs (1959) commented that a person's self- concept what he believes about himself is crucial for his growth and development because he carries his self concept with him to his class, his home and very where. The humanistic Approach has important implications for education as it shifts the focus from teaching to learning. This change of focus is crucially important because students do not always learn what the teacher teaches. Teaching is vitally important for language learning. In the former context but the ultimate consideration is learning that is how much students learn from classroom instruction or teaching. The humanistic Approach to teaching advocated by Moskowitz (1978) and the humanistic psychology of learning has had a significant impact on our present understanding of learning. Education aims to facilitate change and learning which is only possible if one facilitates learning by establishing an interpersonal relationship with the learners.

Humanistic education has a lot of to do with foreign language learning, if the foreign language is taught with positive feelings about themselves and their class mates it will help increase their self esteem and understanding of themselves and others. Once this self actualization occurs students would see the subject matter as self enhancing and related to their lives and they will be motivated to learn to use the foreign language.

Language Programmes based on this approach Motivates learners:

During class activities and exercise the teacher has to build a rapport with learners so that they feel accepted and confident about themselves and their abilities. The class environment should be friendly, supportive, non threatening so that students can overcome their shyness, doubts, tensions and worries and participate in class activities and contribute to the learning process.

Teacher must be a facilitator first:

The teacher's role is important because he/she must facilitate learning and create a learning friendly atmosphere in the class. The teacher must be genuine and true in her/his efforts. He must trust accept and prize students as a worthy individual, she must openly communicate with his/her students and vice-versa,

Secondly, the teacher can add humanistic touch to language teaching in the classroom.

1. Learn student's nerve: it will give them a sense of individually and responsibility.
2. Maintain Eye contact: when interacting with students the teacher can try to appear open and accessible to them.
3. Exchange a little chit chat with the students it makes them important and human.
4. Move around the class: It makes the class seem smaller and increases student involvement and participation.

Thirdly, for improving class participation a learner can take strategies: such as

Divide the class:

Divide the class into groups according to ability and aptitude. This creates a positive learning atmosphere and helps both weak and bright learners. Engage group work have students participate in group work especially co- operative learning in order to develop social and affective skills ensure.

Plans ensure the participation:

Give instructions objectives and time management guidelines at the onset this saves time and the work is done.

Give reward:

Give credit and encouragement for participation in class activities and show your appreciation every time.

Exchange ideas:

Ask students to contribute materials, topics and ideas for their class it boosts their confidence

Permit to work individually:

Accept the learners individual differences let the work their won place

Give assist & support:

Assist while they work help students having problems. Provide general support and approval help the students learn to set realistic goals ensure best accuse of

Forget Language:

Try to keep them using as much of the target language as is possible for them.

Research Questions

This research attempts to answer the following unresolved questions:

Firstly, what are the pivotal problems of Humanistic approach to ELT in Bangladesh?

Secondly, how can we get rid of these menaces to make sure the solution in Language teaching in Bangladesh?

Objective of the study

The study will be done for satisfying the following objectives:

- (a) **Broad Objective:** The study is to analyze the major barriers in Humanistic approach to ELT (English Language Teaching) system during class room teaching and higher education stages in Bangladesh. In doing so, priority will be given to trace out the crucial loopholes of existing system in comparison with a standard philosophy.
- (b) **Specific Objectives:** The specific objectives of the study are as follows:

- (i) To argue why the system of investigation of the effective aspects of language learning by the learner's may lose any chance of retrieving the system of ELT by Humanistic approach from the malaise it has been suffering from.
- (ii) To examine whether existing philosophy and trends at the policy level are worthy anymore and what would be the future trends in ELT in Bangladesh.

Methodology

Nature of Study: This is an applied research which aims at solving specific practical problems. It is concerned with generating new information to serve current needs, solve problems or develop alternatives. To attain the objectives of the study the following research methods will be applied-

- (a) **Survey method:** This method is selected to get inputs from face-to-face interview through a semi-structured questionnaire survey with a large number of stakeholders of effective Language learning system in Bangladesh (i.e. teachers, students, researcher & fellow, and some key persons whose role is very crucial during learning stages and to record their understanding on the realities of the problem. *The students, teachers* to the Universities of Language center, and experts on the subjects will also be interviewed. The entire experimental method to observe cases from beginning to end is not adopted in this research due to the uncertainty involved in the humanistic approach and time constraint of the research. Therefore, survey method is adopted as it will be the most suitable scientific method for collecting cross-section data for this research.
- (b) **Observation and consultation:** Since many qualitative aspects of the problem many not be clearly addressed through semi-structured questionnaire survey mentioned earlier, few observation of CLT & ELT cases will be made to get firsthand knowledge on how students, learners and service providers are struggling with this system. Further, consultations will be conducted at a later stage of the research to collect relevant details on different important issues surfaced through questionnaire survey and observations made earlier.

Probable outcome of the Research:

At present in a situation like ours, there is a real need for language teachers to subscribe to humanistic Approach with from faith its psychological foundation. Because humanistic education is concerned while educating and emotional dimension In the traditional education methods the subject content was poured into the students who were taken to be empty vessels waiting to be filled up by the teachers on the On the other hand in humanistic method a classroom becomes lively and which is full of learning activities in which students actively and enthusiastically participate and they are respected as human beings by the teachers. A learner in an individual method who needs to understand himself and communicate himself to others.

Implications of the Humanistic Approach in the Context of Bangladesh

In an ideal language classroom where achieving communicative competence is the main objective of learning, the relation between the learner and the teacher is vitally important. As the learners are to respect and obey their teachers, the teachers, too, should value the feelings and emotions of the learners. But in our culture it is commonly seen that the learners respect their teachers whereas the teachers, taking this advantage, dominate the class almost as dictators. Obviously, in such a class the situation appears as a barrier to enhancing communicative competence. Here, the humanistic approach suggests that the teachers should have, as the learners have, respected for the emotions and feelings of the learners. No doubt, in the atmosphere where the teacher is a mediator, a facilitator, a motivator, a co-participant, but in no way a dictator, learners learn the language best.

In a pleasant, non-threatening and congenial learning environment, the learner can perform and practice independently and gradually reach his optimum goal. But in our context we see a distorted, despicable and dismal picture of language classroom where the teacher controls everything and the learner is a passive recipient of what is given. In many cases the learners even cannot express their feelings, ask any question or talk at all in the classroom. In this situation we can have benefit from humanistic teaching since it affirms that a non-threatening classroom environment is a must for the language learner to develop the language skills.

It would not be unwise to say that the more actively the learners are involved in the classroom activities, the more rapidly and successfully will they learn the target language. But, regrettably in the traditional classrooms of our country, learners are still treated as empty vessels or mere passive recipients. Though Bangladesh still sticks to the misconception of treating

learners as empty vessels, huge researches show that learners should be the centre of the learning process including all classroom procedures and activities. To learn the language faster and more effectively, the learners must be involved in the classroom activities emotionally and intellectually. Supporting this view, Breen and Candlin remark that the learner “should contribute as much as he gains, and thereby learn in an independent way” (cited in Richards and Rodgers, 1980). This is one of the striking implications of humanistic language teaching. Therefore, the language learners in Bangladesh can have maximum benefit if the principles of the humanistic approach are strictly implemented.

In our country it is still seen that students memorize paragraphs, letters, applications, essays etc. That is the picture of cramming just before the examination and vomiting in the examination is very common. This is why, when the students go outside the classroom. They cannot effectively use the language in real life situations. Humanistic teaching advocates fostering creativity and confidence in language learners. It is believed that the learner, to learn a foreign language successfully, will emotionally engage himself in the learning process, creatively construct meaning by participating in authentic and genuine classroom activities in which making errors is thought to be an integral part of effective learning. Therefore, humanistic teaching can of course, be a constructive suggestion for the teachers in our context who are still on wrong track of leading the learners towards cramming instead of creativity.

Humanistic language teaching encourages pair work as well as group work. It also focuses on the learner’s ideas and realizations are marvelously diverse. As in Bangladesh in one language classroom the teacher has to deal with more than fifty students on average, he, following the humanistic model can design the classroom activities with pair work and group work. Again, when the students are of heterogeneous linguistic levels, the teacher can allow autonomy to every individual learner so that he can grow up in an independent way.

Conclusion

Humanistic approach to teaching seeks to emphasize that the effective aspects of language learning are as important as the cognitive aspects. That is both affective and effective aspects are equally important in language learning. Therefore, teachers pay attention to the students emotional state which has a considerable impact on their language performance and practices? In a non-threatening and pleasurable environment that humanistic teaching offers, learners grow the ability of learning autonomy and feel motivated to learning new linguistic

behaviors. So in language teaching, teachers should consider the affective factors to achieve in language teaching. Though humanistic language teaching has been supported by many scholars, there are some opponents who are dead against it . For example, Gadd(1998) finds fault with English teachers for using techniques which involve the emotions or the inner self. He also speaks of liberation the teacher from the inappropriate and oppressive role of nature of the inner self. Actually, Gadd's arguments are either not well founded or misleading. No humanistic teachers or theorists ever talk substituting the cognitive for effective, but rather about adding the affective, both to facilitate the cognitive in language learning and to encourage the development of the whole person"(Arnold, 1998). Besides, such problems are solved if it is kept in mind that humanistic teaching is not conceived of as something to be imposed from above upon an unwilling teacher or to be prescribed for all teacher.

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About the Author:

Mrs. Ferdousi Akter

Assistant Prof English at Islamic University, Department of English. She completed her Master of Arts in English From Dhaka University on 2010 and research interest focus on English Language & Literature.

Md. Al Mamun

Assistant Prof at Jagannath University, Dhaka Bangladesh.

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